

Synthesis, spectroscopic and antibacterial studies of mono- and bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives with thiohydantoin

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Manuscript received 12 December 2006, accepted 21 March 2007

Abstract : The reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) chloride with a new series of heterocyclic thione i.e. thiohydantoin (LH) have been studied in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran in the presence an amine and complexes of the types $[(C_5H_5)_2TiCl(L)]$ and $[(C_5H_5)Ti(L)_3]$ were obtained. Tentative structural conclusions are drawn for these reaction products based upon elemental analyses, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (UV-VIS, IR and ¹H NMR) data. Attempts have been made to establish a correlation between antibacterial activity and the structures of the products.

Keywords : Titanium(IV), thiohydantoin, antibacterial activity.

The heterocyclic thiones are characterized by thione-thiol tautomerism¹⁻³. They have wide ranging applications and a coordination chemistry that makes extensive use of the exocyclic thione sulphur atom in both conventional and organometallic complexes³. Heterocyclic thiones are weak acids with pK_a values in the range 5–11. The molecules are readily deprotonated by either aqueous or alcoholic NaOH or KOH. Organic bases such as trimethylamine or triethylamine are invariably effective deprotonating agents in most organic solvents. Deprotonation of heterocyclic thiones produces the corresponding thiones in which the negative charge is localized on the thionato sulphur atom and the thioamide π-electron density is concentrated between the carbon and nitrogen atoms of the thioamide. These thionates are ambidentate ligands that are capable of involving either the exocyclic sulphur (η^1-S) or the endocyclic nitrogen (η^1-N) atoms of their thioamide groups¹. The formation of four membered S,N-chelates by heterocyclic thionates is also widespread. Such coordination is characterized by short metal-nitrogen bonds, relatively long metal-sulphur bonds, small chelating angles and mostly planar chelate rings. Although the reported complexes are primarily mononuclear species, there is some evidence that those ligands containing heterocyclic groups with additional donor sites, such as the N atom of some pyrimidine derivatives, may be induced to generate

polynuclear species¹.

In the present communication, the synthesis and characterization of mono- and bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives containing one important class of heterocyclic thione i.e. (thiohydantoin) as chelating agents are reported.

The structures of the 1-aryl-2-thiohydantoin are given below (1).

R = C₆H₅ (PThH), C₆H₄CH₃ (TThH), C₆H₅CH₂ (BThH), C₆H₄Cl-*p* (PCThH), C₆H₄Cl-*o* (CPTThH)

Results and discussion

The reactions of bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride with 1-aryl-2-thiohydantoin (LH) in 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 molar ratios, respectively, in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran in the presence of amine yielded complexes of the types $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2Ti(L)Cl]$ and $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)Ti(L)_3]$ according to the following equations.

The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The methods used for the preparation and isolation of these compounds give materials of good purity as supported by their analyses. All these complexes are colored. They are thermally stable but decompose in the temperature range 135–230 °C. They are quite stable in air but their solutions on long standing get hydrolyzed. Conductance measurements in DMF reveal that they are essentially non-electrolytes. Magnetic susceptibility values at room temperature show the diamagnetic nature of the complexes. The electronic spectra of all these complexes show a band in region 23200–24500 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the charge-transfer band and is in accordance⁶ with the (n - 1)d⁰ns⁰ electronic configuration of titanium.

Infrared spectra :

Thiohydantoin contains a thioamide group. Organic

compounds having a thioamide group (HNC=S) give rise⁸ to four thioamide bands in IR spectra. These are thioamide-I at about 1560–1550 cm⁻¹, band-II at about 1400–1300 cm⁻¹, band-III at about 1090–1080 cm⁻¹ and band-IV at about 850–700 cm⁻¹. These bands have contributions from δ(C-H) + δ(N-H), ν(C=S) + ν(C=N) + δ(C-H), ν(C-N) + ν(C=S) and ν(C=S) modes of vibrations, respectively. In the present ligands, these bands appear at ca. 1500, 1400–1350, 1050 and 880–840 cm⁻¹, respectively. These bands are expected to be affected differently by different modes of coordination after complexation with the metal ions⁵. The appearance of these four bands indicates the existence of ligands in the thione form in the solid state. In solution (basic) IR spectra of the ligands, all these bands were absent but one weak band at ca. 2480 cm⁻¹ appears, assignable to ν(S-H). These facts indicate the possibility of thione ⇌ thiol tautomerism in the solution. In the spectra of complexes all thioamide bands as well as (S-H) band are absent, suggesting coordination of the sulphur atom to the titanium atom in the thiol form. The ν(Ti-S) vibration appears at 400–370 cm⁻¹.

The infrared spectra of the l-aryl-2-thiohydantoin

Table 1. Reactions of Cp₂TiCl₂ with l-aryl-2-thiohydantoin

Reactants (g)	Stirring time (h)	Products, colour, (yield %)	Mol. formula (formula wt.)	Calcd. (Found) %				
				C	H	S	Ti	Cl
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + PThH + Et ₃ N (0.75 + 0.58 + 0.3)	40	Cp ₂ TiCl(PTh) Brown (66)	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ OSTi (404.4)	56.4 (56.0)	4.2 (4.0)	7.9 (7.8)	11.8 (11.7)	8.7 (8.5)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + PThH + n-BuNH ₂ (0.50 + 1.15 + 0.3)	52	CpTi(PTh) ₃ Dark brown (62)	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₃ S ₃ Ti (685.9)	55.9 (55.7)	3.8 (3.5)	14.0 (13.9)	7.0 (6.9)	-
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + TThH + Et ₃ N (0.75 + 0.60 + 0.3)	40	Cp ₂ TiCl(TTh) Yellow (60)	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ OSTi (418.4)	57.4 (57.1)	4.5 (4.3)	7.6 (7.4)	11.4 (11.4)	8.5 (8.3)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₃ + TThH + n-BuNH ₂ (0.50 + 1.25 + 0.3)	50	CpTi(TTh) ₃ Brown (60)	C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₃ S ₃ Ti (727.9)	57.7 (57.5)	4.4 (4.3)	13.2 (13.1)	6.6 (6.5)	-
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + BThH + Et ₃ N (0.75 + 0.60 + 0.3)	45	Cp ₂ TiCl(BTh) Brown (65)	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ OSTi (418.4)	57.4 (57.1)	4.5 (4.4)	7.6 (7.3)	11.4 (11.2)	8.5 (8.4)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₃ + BThH + n-BuNH ₂ (0.50 + 1.25 + 0.3)	52	CpTiCl(BTh) ₃ Red brown (55)	C ₃₅ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₃ S ₃ Ti (727.9)	57.7 (57.5)	4.4 (4.2)	13.2 (13.1)	6.6 (6.5)	-
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + PCTH + Et ₃ N (0.75 + 0.68 + 0.3)	42	Cp ₂ TiCl(PCTH) Brick red (60)	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ OSTi (438.9)	52.0 (51.9)	3.6 (3.6)	7.3 (7.1)	10.9 (10.7)	16.2 (16.2)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₃ + PCTH + n-BuNH ₂ (0.50 + 1.35 + 0.3)	52	CpTi(PCTh) ₃ Red (55)	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ Cl ₃ N ₆ O ₃ S ₃ Ti (789.4)	48.6 (48.2)	2.9 (2.5)	12.2 (12.0)	6.1 (6.0)	13.5 (13.3)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₂ + CPThH + Et ₃ N (0.75 + 0.68 + 0.3)	40	Cp ₂ TiCl(CPTh) Brown (68)	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ OSTi (438.9)	52.0 (51.8)	3.6 (3.6)	7.3 (7.2)	10.9 (10.9)	16.1 (16.0)
Cp ₂ TiCl ₃ + CPThH + n-BuNH ₂ (0.50 + 1.35 + 0.3)	50	CpTi(CPTh) ₃ Brown (58)	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ Cl ₃ N ₆ O ₃ S ₃ Ti (789.4)	48.6 (48.3)	2.9 (2.5)	12.2 (12.1)	6.1 (6.1)	13.5 (13.2)

ligands show bands at *ca.* 3300 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$. In the complexes this band is absent. In the solution IR spectra of the ligands, one band appears at *ca.* 1600–1580 cm^{-1} , assignable³ to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ and formed as a result of thione-thiol tautomerism. In the complexes, this band shifts to lower frequency which may be taken as evidence for the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to titanium. This is further confirmed by the appearance of new bands around 450–420 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(\text{Ti-N})$.

A sharp band appearing at 1720–1700 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C=O})$ in the spectra of the ligands appears at the same place in the spectra of the complexes, ruling out the possibility of coordination through the carbonyl group.

In addition, absorption bands occurring at $\sim 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\nu(\text{C-H})$, $\sim 1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\nu(\text{C-C})$ and $\sim 1020 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ $\delta(\text{C-H})$ in all the complexes indicate the presence a cyclopentadienyl ring. All of these bands are similar to those of mono-/bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV). It has been pointed out⁷ that at 3000 cm^{-1} , $\eta^1\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$ should show four bands whereas $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$ should show only one. In the complexes reported in this paper, only one band at 3000 cm^{-1} indicates the pentahapto nature of the cyclopentadienyl ring.

Thus, it becomes evident that the ligands act as bidentate chelating agents, coordinating through the thiol-sulphur and azomethine nitrogen.

¹H NMR spectra :

The proton NMR spectra of these complexes were recorded in deuterated chloroform and dimethylsulphoxide; the intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. In general, a slight low field shift of the resonance signals of various protons (R) in these complexes, in comparison with the respective pro-

ton signals in the free ligands, may be attributed to deshielding upon coordination. The resonance signal for the protons on the C_5H_5 ring always falls near δ 6.5–6.85 ppm. The two kinetic possibilities, viz. metal-centered rearrangement is slow or fast, may be distinguished by analysis of the NMR spectra. In the spectra of the 1 : 3 derivatives $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ti}(\text{L})_3$, two distinct resonance lines for the protons of the ligands are observed which must result from the non-equivalent environments for the various ligands. The spectra of l-aryl-2-thiohydantoin show one sharp signal at δ 4.8–4.92 due to the NH proton which is absent in the corresponding complexes. The signals due to the aromatic ring appear in the range δ 7.25–7.48. The integrated proton ratios correspond to the proposed formulae.

Thus, on the basis of the above studies, the structures (2) may be proposed for $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{L})\text{Cl}]$ and $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ti}(\text{L})_3]$.

(2)

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of the complexes together with parent ligands has been screened against Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* by the paper disk plate method at 1000 ppm concentration. The inhibition zone (mm) around each plate was

Table 2. Proton chemical shifts (δ , ppm) at 25 °C of the complexes

Complex	C_5H_5	Aromatic ring	CH_2	CH_3
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}(\text{PTh})]$	6.60s	7.42s	3.20s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{PTh})_3]$	6.55s	7.42s, 7.25s	3.25s, 3.12s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}(\text{TTh})]$	6.65s	7.38s	3.30s	2.10s
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{TTh})_3]$	6.50s	7.35s, 7.20m	3.28s, 3.15s	2.15s, 2.00s
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}(\text{BTh})]$	6.85s	7.40s	3.25s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{BTh})_3]$	6.75s	7.38s, 7.25s	3.22s, 3.18s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}(\text{PCTh})]$	6.70s	7.48m	3.22s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{PCTh})_3]$	6.62s	7.45m, 7.32m	3.20s, 3.10s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}(\text{CPTh})]$	6.78s	7.45m	3.20s	-
$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{CPTh})_3]$	6.68s	7.48m, 7.38m	3.20s, 3.12s	-

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of the ligands and their corresponding complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
PThH	8	9
[Cp ₂ TiCl(PTh)]	12	14
[CpTi(PTh) ₃]	10	10
TThH	12	10
[Cp ₂ TiCl(TTh)]	16	15
[CpTi(TTh) ₃]	14	13
BThH	10	8
[Cp ₂ TiCl(BTh)]	14	12
[CpTi(BTh) ₃]	12	10
PCThH	12	11
[Cp ₂ TiCl(PCTh)]	20	17
[CpTi(PCTh) ₃]	15	14
CPThH	12	10
[Cp ₂ Ti(CPTh)]	20	18
[CpTi(CPTh) ₃]	17	15
Ampicillin	35	35

measured after 24 h and the results of these studies are listed in Table 3. The results lead to the following conclusions :

(a) The complexes are slightly more toxic than the parent ligands.

(b) Bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives possess better activity than mono(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) derivatives.

(c) The best activity was recorded with derivatives of ligands PCThH and CPThH, i.e. containing -Cl group at phenyl ring of thiohydantoin.

Experimental

All of the reactions were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. Tetrahydrofuran (Merck) was dried by sodium wire overnight and then refluxed until it gave a blue colour with benzophenone. Triethylamine and *n*-butylamine were purified by the reported method⁴. The ligand thiohydantoin was prepared as mentioned in the literature⁵. The details of analyses and physical measurements are the same as described earlier⁶.

Reaction of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride with 1-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin (molar ratio 1 : 1) :

A mixture of 1-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin (0.58 g, 3.0

mmol) and triethylamine (0.3 g, 3.0 mmol) was stirred in dry tetrahydrofuran (50 mL) for 15 min and then bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride (0.75 g, 3.0 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 40 h at room temperature. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The brown coloured complex, so obtained, was crystallised from tetrahydrofuran and was found to be [(C₅H₅)₂TiCl(C₉H₇N₂SO)]; yield 66%.

Reaction of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride with 1-phenyl-2-thiohydantoin (molar ratio 1 : 3, respectively) :

1-Phenyl-2-thiohydantoin (1.15 g, 5.9 mmol) was dissolved in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (60 mL) and to this *n*-butylamine was added and the mixture was stirred for 10 min. To this, bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride (0.5 g, 2.0 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 52 h. The precipitated coloured complex was filtered and thoroughly washed with tetrahydrofuran. It was found to be [(C₅H₅)Ti(C₉H₇N₂SO)₃]; yield 62%.

The same synthetic procedure was used for the reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) chloride with different thiohydantoin such as 1-*m*-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin, 1-benzyl-2-thiohydantoin, 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-2-thiohydantoin, 1-*o*-chlorophenyl-2-thiohydantoin in molar ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 3, respectively. The details of these reactions are given in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. D. S. Moore and S. D. Robinson, *Adv. Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **32**, 171.
2. E. S. Raper, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **153**, 199.
3. S. K. Sengupta, O. P. Pandey, A. Rai and A. Sinha, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 150.
4. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry including Qualitative Organic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans, London, 1956.
5. V. Srivastava, O. P. Pandey, S. K. Sengupta and S. C. Tripathi, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1985, **279**, 395.
6. A. K. Srivastava, O. P. Pandey and S. K. Sengupta, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 1405.
7. E. Hey-Hawkins, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **94**, 1661.